

**PSYCHOLOGICAL PRENATAL CARE IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE: AN
EXPERIENCE REPORT**

ATENCIÓN PSICOLÓGICA PRENATAL EN LA ATENCIÓN PRIMARIA DE SALUD: RELATO DE
UNA EXPERIENCIA

O PRÉ-NATAL PSICOLÓGICO NA ATENÇÃO PRIMÁRIA À SAÚDE: UM RELATO DE
EXPERIÊNCIA

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Manuscrito submetido em: 20 de setembro de 2024.

Aprovado em: 23 de junho de 2025.

Publicado em: 01 de agosto de 2025.

Abstract

Psychological prenatal care encompasses the emotional and sociocultural changes that women experience during pregnancy, allowing for comprehensive care. It works as an important tool in primary health care, allowing the construction of the mother-baby bond, the strengthening of their support network, the listening and acceptance of fears, anxieties and anxieties. Thus, the objective was to describe the actions developed by a psychologist in a Family Health Unit, in the care of pregnant and puerperal women, through psychological prenatal care. This is a qualitative study, of the experience report type, with a Family Health Unit in southern Bahia as its location, which houses a Multiprofessional Residency Program in Family Health, carried out between the months of January and December 2023. The psychologist sought to intervene through initial care, psychoeducational activities, shared consultation with other professionals and puerperal assessment in order to detect risk factors for mental disorders during pregnancy, parturition and puerperium, in addition to articulation and interdisciplinary action in the search for comprehensive care in this phase of the reproductive cycle. It is concluded that the actions of the psychologist in psychological prenatal care are extremely important because they allow the improvement of mental health care for pregnant women, their partners and family members.

Keywords: Prenatal care; Psychology; Primary health care; Qualitative research.

Resumen

La atención psicológica prenatal abarca los cambios emocionales y socioculturales que las mujeres experimentan durante el embarazo, permitiendo una atención integral. Funciona como una herramienta importante en la atención primaria de salud, permitiendo la construcción del vínculo madre-bebé, el fortalecimiento de su red de apoyo, escuchando y acogiendo miedos, ansiedades y ansiedades. Así, el objetivo fue describir las acciones desarrolladas por una psicóloga en una Unidad

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de Salud de la Familia, en la atención a mujeres embarazadas y puérperas, a través de la atención psicológica prenatal. Se trata de un estudio cualitativo, del tipo relato de experiencia, realizado en una Unidad de Salud de la Familia del sur de Bahía, que alberga un Programa de Residencia Multiprofesional en Salud de la Familia, realizado entre enero y diciembre de 2023. La psicóloga buscó intervenir a través de la atención inicial, las actividades de psicoeducación, la consulta compartida con otros profesionales y la evaluación puerperal, con el fin de detectar factores de riesgo para trastornos mentales durante el embarazo, parto y puerperio, además de la articulación y la acción interdisciplinaria en la búsqueda de una atención integral en esta fase del ciclo reproductivo. Se concluye que las acciones del psicólogo en la atención psicológica prenatal son sumamente importantes porque permiten mejorar la atención de la salud mental de las gestantes, sus parejas y familiares.

Palabras-clave: Atención prenatal; Psicología; Atención primaria de salud; Investigación cualitativa.

Resumo

O pré-natal psicológico abarca as alterações emocionais e socioculturais que a mulher vivencia durante a gestação, permitindo um atendimento integral. Funciona como uma importante ferramenta na atenção primária à saúde, permitindo a construção do vínculo mãe-bebê, o fortalecimento da sua rede de apoio, a escuta e o acolhimento dos medos, angústias e ansiedades. Desse modo, instituiu-se como objetivo: descrever as ações desenvolvidas por uma psicóloga em uma Unidade de Saúde da Família, no atendimento a gestantes e puérperas, por meio do pré-natal psicológico. Trata-se de um estudo qualitativo, do tipo relato de experiência, tendo como local uma Unidade de Saúde da Família do sul da Bahia, que abriga um Programa de Residência Multiprofissional em Saúde da Família, realizado entre os meses de janeiro e dezembro de 2023. A psicóloga(o) buscou intervir através do atendimento inicial, de atividades de psicoeducação, da consulta compartilhada com outros profissionais e da avaliação puerperal a fim de detectar os fatores de risco para transtornos mentais durante a gestação, parturição e puerpério além da articulação e atuação interdisciplinar na busca pela integralidade do cuidado nessa fase do ciclo reproductivo. Conclui-se que as ações da psicóloga no pré-natal psicológico são de extrema importância por permitir a melhoria da assistência à saúde mental de gestantes, suas parcerias e familiares.

Palavras-chave: Cuidado pré-natal; Psicologia; Atenção primária à saúde; Pesquisa qualitativa.

Introduction

Pregnancy is a significant and remarkable experience in the lives of some women, their partners and families, but some feelings and symptoms of anxiety and stress may arise at this stage, triggering emotional, social, professional, marital and family dynamic changes (Soares et al., 2021).

Perinatal psychology aims to study all the psychological phenomena that occur around the birth of a baby, that is, during reproductive planning, pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period. It arises to prevent and remedy situations of distress that may arise during this period, seeking psychological preparation for motherhood (Soares et al., 2021).

Thus, psychological prenatal care (PNP) emerges as a complement to traditional prenatal care, focusing on psychoprophylaxis during the pregnancy-puerperal period, since it focuses on the emotional and sociocultural changes that women experience during pregnancy, childbirth and the puerperium, allowing comprehensive care for women, through socio-emotional and psychoeducational support (Benincasa et al., 2019).

Furthermore, it is an important tool in Primary Health Care (PHC), reinforced by Bill 4,432/20, which makes psychological and/or psychiatric care mandatory for pregnant women in the Unified Health System (SUS), providing opportunities for attentive listening, addressing fears, anxieties and worries surrounding the perinatal period and the well-being of mother and child with a reduction in complications and risks, such as postpartum depression (Arrais; Araújo; Shiavo, 2019; Brasil, 2020).

It is worth noting that, in a survey carried out with 330 postpartum women in a public maternity hospital in the interior of Espírito Santo, it was found that the prevalence of symptoms of postpartum depression (PPD) was 29.7% and among the risk factors were the low level of affective and emotional social support, something that can be worked on by the PNP (Santos et al., 2022).

Therefore, this study is justified by the importance of psychologists' role in prenatal, childbirth, and postpartum care, especially in PHC, with an emphasis on humanizing and promoting maternal/fetal mental health. Therefore, the guiding question was: What actions can a psychologist perform in the care of pregnant and postpartum women through the PNP? The general objective was to describe the actions performed by a psychologist in a Family Health Unit (FHU) in the care of pregnant and postpartum women through the PNP, in order to contribute to the development of knowledge in this field.

The social and scientific relevance of this study is evident as it reveals the actions developed by a psychologist to prevent risks and/or promote health and well-being for mothers and their children, and can be applied in other scenarios.

Methodology

This is a descriptive, qualitative, experience-report study. The research aims to describe the actions developed by a psychologist at a Family Health Unit (FHU) in providing care to pregnant and postpartum women through the PNP (National Program for Nursing

Practice), with the aim of contributing to the development of knowledge in this field. It is a theoretical-practical construction that aims to refine knowledge about the experience itself, based on the researcher's perspective within a specific cultural and historical context (Daltro; Faria, 2019).

The experience took place between January and December 2023 at a USF in southern Bahia. The selected USF houses a Family Health Residency Program at a public university and has a health services manager; two nurses; two physicians; a dental surgeon; 15 community health workers; two receptionists, an administrative assistant, an oral health technician, three nursing technicians, a pharmacist, two pharmacy assistants, and a general services professional. In addition, the multidisciplinary team includes two resident nurses, a resident nutritionist, a resident physical therapist, a resident social worker, and a resident psychologist.

It should be noted that this report will present and discuss the actions developed by a psychologist in the care of pregnant and postpartum women through the PNP, which involves four to six monthly meetings with pregnant women and their support network, as well as group activities involving other professionals such as community health agents (CHAs), nurses, dentists, doctors, and pharmacists. The invitation to participate in the PNP was made during prenatal consultations conducted by nurses at the FHU.

The data were collected using the participant observation technique, which allows the researcher to observe actions, interactions or events that occur and record them in a field diary, with subsequent analysis of the observed processes and the researcher's impressions, offering the opportunity to obtain information through the experience of the phenomena themselves (Campos; Silva; Albuquerque, 2021; Kroef; Gavillon; Ramm, 2020).

During the interventions, instruments were used to identify and monitor symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress during pregnancy. The first is the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI), which consists of 21 items that use an intensity scale in relation to the symptoms experienced, ranging from 0 (indicating that the symptom was not experienced) to 3 (indicating that the symptom was experienced with severe intensity). The second is the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II), which encompasses a 21-item scale aimed at measuring the intensity of depression, which can be mild, moderate, or severe. The third is the

Perceived Stress Scale, consisting of 14 questions that measure how often a person experiences stress-related feelings and thoughts. Specifically for the postpartum period, there is the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), a 10-question instrument that explores various emotional aspects experienced in the postpartum period for early detection of PPD. Both the BAI and BDI-II are for the exclusive use of psychologists; the other scales can be used by all healthcare professionals (Arrais; Araújo; Shiavo, 2019).

It is important to note that the research upheld all ethical principles involving scientific production, preserving the data of all professionals involved and the study location.

Results

The PNP, at the selected unit, emerged as an important space for mothers, partners, and family members to share their experiences, fantasies, fears, anxieties, joys, and sorrows arising from this process, and to exchange experiences and build together the new parental role. Thus, the psychologist sought to intervene through initial care focusing on the pregnant woman's psychological changes, psychoeducation activities, shared consultations, and postpartum evaluation, as presented below:

- Initial cares

During the first meeting, the psychologist conducted an anamnesis to learn more about each pregnant woman, allowing her to express her emotions, expectations, and experiences regarding pregnancy. The first-time mothers reported fear of childbirth and fetal loss. The multigravidas, in turn, highlighted their previous birth experiences and their fears and anxieties regarding the new pregnancy. The presence or absence of nausea and vomiting was observed, as their persistence and severity may be related to psychological factors and the existence of pre-existing or familial mental disorders. In the case of pregnant adolescents, a vulnerable group, the impact of pregnancy on this stage of life and its impact on school dropout rates were assessed.

Associated with this, a semi-structured interview was conducted, which consisted of the application of a psychological investigation instrument for pregnant women with the objective of identifying risk and protective factors for the development of emotional changes with a detailed assessment of the need for referral to a psychosocial outpatient clinic or for monitoring with other professionals (psychiatrist, neurologist, among others).

This instrument made it possible to collect the socioeconomic characteristics (age, marital status, period of pregnancy, current occupation, individual and family income) of the pregnant woman and her family nucleus and the main psychological changes during the gestational period, being divided into three parts:

First trimester

In this early stage of pregnancy, the psychological instrument focuses on the following issues: presence and number of children; occurrence of miscarriage prior to the current pregnancy; provision and location of prenatal care; discovery and planning of the pregnancy; importance of psychological support during pregnancy and presence of a support network. During the questions, the psychologist asked the pregnant woman to express her fears, anxieties, and guilt, if she felt comfortable.

Second trimester

During this second stage of pregnancy, the pregnant woman's perception of bodily changes; physical and emotional sensations surrounding the baby's movements; discovery of the baby's sex and level of satisfaction; acceptance of the pregnancy by family and partners and changes in libido were assessed. During the interview, the psychologist observed and identified possible emotional changes, fragility in family and marital relationships, and feelings about the biological transformations, especially a drop in libido, denoting guilt, low self-esteem and repercussions on sexual life with partners on the part of some pregnant women.

Third trimester

In the last stage of pregnancy, sleep patterns, the presence of nightmares, and the level of anxiety were assessed; development of any health problems; knowledge and preference for the mode of delivery and birth; fears about childbirth; feelings about being a mother; knowledge about pregnant women's rights; desires about breastfeeding, and the presence of fear after the baby's birth.

Through the instrument, the impact of risk and protective factors on the mental health of pregnant women was noted, through listening and accepting complaints with subsequent psychoeducation and interventions according to the context and needs of each one.

- Psychoeducation and psychological interventions

Psychoeducational activities comprise the PNP and were carried out with the pregnant woman and her support network, through the preparation and distribution of informative leaflets on physical, emotional and sociocultural changes that occur during pregnancy, with subsequent discussion and clarification of doubts.

First trimester

In the first gestational period, psychoeducational activities covered mood changes such as ambivalence and irritability; the psychologist's duties in prenatal care and in cases of recent fetal loss, a time in which individual, marital, and family adaptations to mourning for the unborn child who is not socially recognized were worked on, with the expression of feelings such as guilt, failure, and helplessness.

Second trimester

During the second gestational period, psychoeducational activities focused on the importance of the hormone oxytocin for labor; the formation of the mother-baby-partner bond; and breastfeeding, with a focus on emotional and affective aspects. Counseling was

also provided on the loss or increase of libido during pregnancy, noting how these changes can affect the pregnant woman's perspective as a woman.

Third trimester

During the third gestational stage, psychoeducational strategies addressed the types of birth, the birth plan, and the occurrence of obstetric violence, which can result in physical and emotional harm, leading to anxiety disorders, sleep disturbances, post-traumatic stress, and depressive symptoms. Breathing and relaxation techniques were taught to reduce the high levels of anxiety associated with the approach to birth, as well as actions to strengthen the sense of security for the new cycle that begins with the baby's birth.

In the three cases where significant emotional changes were observed, validated tests were administered, such as the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II), the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI), and the Perceived Stress Scale. The results obtained through the fully administered instruments guided the psychologist in conducting subsequent prenatal psychological sessions, using cognitive behavioral techniques to reduce the symptoms presented. The presence of anxiety and stress symptoms was observed, mainly related to excessive work hours, lack of social support, family and marital conflicts, and uncertainty related to motherhood.

Furthermore, a moderate risk of anxiety was observed in pregnant women, associated with fear of fetal loss and childbirth itself. Regarding the assessment of depressive symptoms, a high risk was observed in only one pregnant woman who had previously been diagnosed, which guided the health team in monitoring care in Primary Care and referring her to High-Risk Prenatal Care.

- Shared consultation

In order to promote comprehensive care in the PNP, shared consultations were held between the psychologist and other professionals such as nurses, nutritionists, physiotherapists and social workers, which made it possible to expand knowledge about the gestational process, sharing knowledge from different areas.

The consultations aimed to promote comprehensive care for pregnant women through interprofessional collaboration, assessing their needs and their authorization for shared care. For those who were socially vulnerable or had little knowledge of pregnant women's rights, the social worker participated in the consultations to provide guidance on maternity leave/pay and specific social programs for this group.

In turn, during consultations with the physiotherapist, lower back pain was managed, mainly because it acts as a stress intensifier. Furthermore, guidance on the importance of physical activity during pregnancy and its repercussions during delivery was also provided to reduce fear, feelings of helplessness, and anxiety, which are common during this phase.

Regarding the participation of nurses, the systematic monitoring during prenatal care associated with the continuous educational process on topics such as: biopsychosocial transformations of pregnancy, stages of labor, types of births, breastfeeding, among others, stands out.

In consultations with the nutritionist, nutritional assessment is highlighted, a time when the physical, psychological and emotional relationship with food was linked to whether the diet was balanced or not.

- Postpartum evaluation

During the puerperal period, a postpartum consultation was held to assess the user's physical and emotional conditions, with postpartum psychological screening and application of the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EDPS).

Postpartum psychological screening is a guiding tool for psychologists and is divided into two parts: the first assesses risk factors for postpartum mental illness; the second identifies the need for psychotherapy and medication with a psychiatrist. This assessment can be performed from 45 days postpartum until three years postpartum.

The EDPS is a validated instrument adapted for several countries that measures the presence and intensity of depressive symptoms in the last seven days. The instrument

should be administered between 45 days and six months postpartum and can be administered by any healthcare professional.

Thus, the postpartum assessment seeks to identify significant emotional changes. To this end, the psychologist must provide support and guidance on emotional changes during the postpartum period, allowing postpartum women and their families to understand what is expected and common in the postpartum period and to seek help if symptoms indicate progression to other psychological disorders.

Discussion

With the advancement of perinatal psychology, discussions have arisen about the importance of psychologists in public and private health services as support for maternal and child emotional health (Soares et al., 2021). Research conducted with pregnant women using the SUS (Unified Health System) highlights the need for a professional with an attentive eye, since there is a high frequency of emotional changes during this phase (Arrais; Araújo; Schiavo, 2019; Shiavo; Perosa, 2020).

Among the numerous possibilities for psychologists to work in, PNP consultations stand out, providing socio-emotional support to pregnant women through assistance in coping with and resolving conflicts, as well as reducing psychosocial risks. Therefore, it is clear that the psychologist, in exercising her role in the PNP, provides preventive psychotherapeutic assistance against possible psychological crises, in order to promote a healthy pregnancy and the pleasant arrival of the baby (Benincasa et al., 2019).

Thus, the psychological consultation offered to pregnant women seeks to clarify doubts and offer information from the perspective of promoting mental health, being a care strategy to investigate the physical, emotional and psychological conditions of pregnant women, considering the social environment and the particularities of each one (Benincasa et al., 2019; Shiavo, 2020).

Psychological care during pregnancy focuses on psychoprophylaxis during the pregnancy-puerperal cycle, providing support and guidance to pregnant women and their support networks. The psychologist's role in the PNP encompasses the stages and feelings of pregnancy, the experience of childbirth and the postpartum period, cases of fetal loss

involving perinatal grief, and increasingly common situations such as anxiety, stress, and postpartum depression, as well as cases of obstetric violence that impact women's lives (Arruda; Coelho, 2022).

Thus, the psychologist's evaluation tools favored the early detection, monitoring, and treatment of emotional changes, as well as the prevention of future physical and emotional complications. This corroborates the Prenatal and Postpartum Guide in Primary Health Care, which emphasizes the importance of mental health care during pregnancy and postpartum, through the early identification of symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress, appropriate treatment, and, if necessary, referral to specialized services (Nicolotti et al., 2024).

Therefore, some actions performed by the psychologist in the PNP should be valued, such as the psychoeducational approach, which proposes adapting educational practices to the pregnant woman's needs and capabilities; offering objective and clear explanations, clarifying doubts; using written resources; encouraging active behavior in the woman; stimulating feedback from the pregnant woman; and using teaching resources as supplementary tasks (Arrais; Araújo; Shiavo, 2019; Carvalho; Malagris; Rangé, 2019; Saldanha et al., 2024). From this perspective, this study observed that pregnant women developed a more active and conscious stance towards the gestational process, since some of these users lacked appropriate knowledge, which favored the creation of fantasies related to motherhood, often shared and endorsed by friends and family, without any scientific evidence.

Therefore, psychoeducation proposes the humanization of care during the gestational process, preventing adverse situations that may affect the experience of a healthy postpartum period (Benincasa et al., 2019; Romero; Cassino, 2018). It is also a treatment modality that integrates psychotherapeutic and educational interventions, encompassing a more holistic perspective based on skills and evidence (Carvalho; Malagris; Rangé, 2019).

Corroborating the studies above, it was found that feelings of fear, anguish, worry and anxiety were related to insecurity and lack of self-confidence in the face of experiences during the gestational period, demonstrating that health education actions enabled the expansion of knowledge and reduction of anxiety symptoms, giving pregnant women more confidence about the pregnancy-puerperal process.

Furthermore, there is shared consultation in the PNP, characterized by a multidimensional, interdisciplinary, efficient and resolute clinic, with therapeutic and educational purposes for the pregnant woman, minimizing unnecessary referrals (Nascimento; Cordeiro, 2019).

Shared care for pregnant women, through joint consultations, specific shifts, and health education activities, was able to fully meet the needs of pregnant women without fragmenting care. To achieve this, professionals need to be trained in shared care, reinforcing the importance of using group strategies as resources for conveying guidelines and sharing experiences (Franco et al., 2020).

Associated with this is the parturition phase, a stage that involves psychological, physical, social, economic, and cultural aspects and is therefore considered a complex event, with the potential to mobilize ambivalent feelings such as anxiety, insecurity, fear, stress, joy, excitement, and anticipation. It is known that women who have experienced traumatic birth experiences, in which they felt violated by the team in charge, may experience difficulties in establishing the mother-baby bond, especially in the postpartum period (Matos; Magalhães; Féres-Carneiro, 2021).

Thus, the psychological consultation in the PNP during the postpartum period provided women with a space to search for meaning in their experience, since many pregnant women expressed their fears and anxieties related to childbirth and the postpartum period, reducing feelings of frustration and fear from previous births, revealing the importance of writing about the emotions experienced and sharing stories to produce the feeling of internally elaborating one's own experience, helping other people who may have gone through or may go through the same experience (Matos; Magalhães; Féres-Carneiro, 2021).

During this period, mood swings may also occur, depending on the experience of pregnancy and childbirth, resulting in baby blues, PPD, or maternal psychosis. Therefore, it is necessary to continue monitoring the woman in the hospital and at home, through the PNP (Souza; Acácio, 2019).

As a limitation of the study, the small number of health units involved in the experience stands out, something overcome by the quality of the description of the psychologist's actions, which can be replicated in other care settings.

Final considerations

It is concluded that the gestational period is full of physical, social, emotional and family changes for pregnant women, in this sense, psychological support is essential for better adaptation of the woman and her partner, from fetal development to the arrival of the child, especially through preventive, educational and interprofessional interventions.

Thus, primary health care is a suitable space to provide comprehensive care to pregnant and postpartum women, as these women may experience mood swings, frequent crying, and anxiety and depression symptoms.

Therefore, the psychologist's actions during the PNP focused on individual care for pregnant women, through consultations that identified risk factors for emotional changes. Related to this issue, psychoeducational activities were highlighted, providing guidance to pregnant women and their families on the psychological processes involved in the pregnancy-postpartum cycle.

Furthermore, shared consultations are a valuable opportunity within primary care to welcome and listen to pregnant women, focusing on shared and interprofessional care for the demands and needs typical of this period. Finally, postpartum assessments contribute to the early detection of mental disorders such as baby blues, PPD, and psychosis, fostering a healthy mother-child, partner-family relationship.

Thus, the importance and scope of psychologists' activities in the PNP are evident, enabling comprehensive care for pregnant women, women in labor, and postpartum women, aiming to improve healthcare for this population group. It is believed that the continued presence of psychologists in primary health care, especially prenatal care, is essential for improving the mental health of pregnant women, partners, and their families, requiring greater government support. Further studies on the PNP are also suggested, enabling the expansion of emotional and psychological strategies for a healthy pregnancy and birth.

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Thematic dossier

EDUCATION, TEACHING AND TRAINING IN MULTIPROFESSIONAL HEALTH RESIDENCES

e-ISSN: 2595-4881

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